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Peculiarities of the Post-Sanctions Reversal of Export Flows in Russia's Forest and Pulp-and-Paper Industries

KEYWORDS

sanctions,
export flows,
domestic market,
exports,
imports,
supply chains,
pulp and paper products,
timber industry

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The study is relevant because the forestry industry plays a vital role in the Russian economy, contributing significantly to GDP, exports, and employment. In the context of sanctions restricting access to foreign markets and complicating logistics, there is a need to develop domestic demand and identify alternative sales channels.

Aim: to analyze the conditions and factors shaping the post-sanctions reversal and regional redistribution of export flows in Russia's forest and pulp-and-paper industries.

Materials and methods. The study draws on statistical reports and the collections Regions of Russia. Socio-economic indicators (2017-2022), as well as articles from scientific journals on economics, regional studies, and the forest industry. The methods included analysis of statistical data, including imports and exports reported by the Central Bank for 2015-2022, as well as the dynamics of the timber industry's development in Russia in 2010-2022.

Results. The study shows that the sustainable development of the timber industry should be based on establishing a new balance between domestic and foreign sales, taking into account the risks of instability in the export-oriented model, the closure of EU markets, logistical constraints, and rising costs for shipments along the southeastern export routes.

Conclusion. The close interdependence of sectoral markets across countries, driven by globalization, led to large-scale losses during the 2020 lockdowns and subsequent sanctions, which in turn deepened the shortage of commodity supplies in the global economy. For Russia's timber industry, the most pressing challenge is the reorientation of export flows towards Asian markets, particularly China.

FOR CITATION

Received: Dec 6, 2024
Accepted: Mar 3, 2025
Published: Jun 1, 2025

Reznikov, S. N., Pavlyukova, A. V., & Tishchenko, I. A. (2025). Peculiarities of the Post-Sanctions Reversal of Export Flows in Russia's Forest and Pulp-and-Paper Industries. *Economic Consultant*, (2), 74–89. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2025.2.5>

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INTRODUCTION

This study is relevant because the timber industry plays a critical role in the Russian economy, significantly contributing to GDP, export revenues, and job creation. Russia is one of the world's leading exporters of forest resources and products such as wood, lumber, pulp, and paper. Recent sanctions restricted access to foreign markets and disrupted supply chains, making it necessary to find new sales channels and to develop the domestic market. Amid sanctions, the need to advance domestic technologies, equipment, and materials for the timber industry is growing. An analysis of the current situation will form long-term strategies for the sector, addressing emerging challenges and opportunities, and will help strengthen national security.

The short overview of the timber industry development in Russia highlights the instability of industrial production and fluctuations in shipments both domestically and internationally since 2020. The spread of COVID-19 and the subsequent lockdowns and restrictions across countries disrupted the operations of industrial enterprises and transportation networks.

In 2022, the development trajectories of the global and Russian timber industries diverged due to intense external sanctions which closed traditional European markets for Russia and caused several adverse effects, including:

- higher transportation costs for finished products;
- realignment of the logistics market, including rerouting and engagement of new suppliers;
- withdrawal of some Western partners from the market;
- strengthening of the ruble.

The fifth European Union sanctions package, introduced in spring 2022, and the seventh and eighth packages in summer and autumn resulted in a sharp reduction of timber product supplies to Europe. Export volumes to the West fell significantly but were partially compensated by redirecting exports to countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

In exports, the substitution of corrugated packaging supplies to Italy, Germany, and Poland is occurring due to increased shipments to Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, and Belarus.

Thus, the current conditions for the development of Russia's timber industry, marked by production instability and disruptions in shipments due to the pandemic and sanctions, underscore the relevance of this study.

The paper aims to analyze the conditions and factors influencing the post-sanction reversal and regional redistribution of export flows of forest and pulp and paper products in Russia's timber industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials for the study included statistical reports and official data, notably the collections *Regions of Russia: Socio-Economic Indicators* for 2017-2022.

Additionally, articles from scientific journals on economics, regional studies, and the forest industry were used, including *Regional Research of Russia*; *Land Use Policy*; *Studies on Russian Economic Development*; *Forestry Engineering Journal*; *Regional Economics: Theory and Practice*; and *Journal of International Wildlife Law & Policy*, among others.

Research methods involved the analysis of statistical data, specifically the imports and exports of wood and pulp and paper products in Russia in 2015-2022, as well as the examination of development trends in the Russian timber industry in 2010-2022.

LITERATURE REVIEW

I. Kuzminov and P. A. Lobanova examine the role of the pulp and paper industry as a key sector within Russia's domestic timber industry and its impact on the country's economic and spatial development. The researchers identified typological groups (or belts) of enterprises in the European part of Russia, characterized by various features for each group, including size, geographic location, development potential, competitiveness, and associated risks [1].

E. Shvarts et al. note that on January 28, 2021, the Strategy for the Development of the Forestry Complex of the Russian Federation until 2030 was discussed and approved. While forestry development remains a well-established policy area, the strategy does not address problems and errors in forest management in recent years. The authors emphasize the need to adjust the approved Strategy and its implementation plan through consultation with leading scientists and practitioners in the forestry sector [2].

D. Dobrynin et al. point out that Russia ranks first globally in terms of abandoned agricultural land overgrown with forest. However, these forests remain informal and unregulated, as current legal categories do not allow landowners to engage in forestry activities. The most feasible options include private forestry, managed by individual landowners, and large-scale industrial forestry, managed by companies [3].

S. D. Tsymbalov et al. highlight several advantages of using wood as a construction material over traditional building materials, including environmental friendliness, good thermal insulation, ease of processing, manufacturability, and cost efficiency [4].

Russia possesses the largest forest reserves in the world. At the same time, countries in Europe and North America are developing more technologically advanced and environmentally sustainable processing methods, focusing on certification and conservation of forest resources. Interaction includes the export of Russian timber and the import of high-tech products, as well as joint initiatives in sustainable forest management and combating illegal logging.

V. Grigoryev explores the prospects for cooperation between Russia and China in the forestry sector. The author proposes several measures to develop collaboration, including establishing an export system via the Northern Sea Route, developing forest plantations, and implementing other progressive management strategies [5].

V. Petrov et al. analyze forestry in Russia and Finland through the lens of economic relations shaped by national forest legislation and state forest management systems. The authors compare the financial efficiency of forestry in the two countries by analyzing costs and revenues [6].

M. Elbakidze et al. conduct a comparative analysis of the forest industry in Sweden and Russia. The researchers note that in Sweden, forestry achieves sustainable profitability through high-investment forest management, whereas in Russia, forestry relies on natural regeneration with minimal investment [7].

Regional disparities are significant in the development of Russia's forest industry. Fuel- and forest-rich regions, such as Siberia and the Far East, have abundant forest reserves and well-developed enterprises, whereas the European part of the country faces limitations due to smaller forest resources and environmental restrictions.

M. A. Shishelov and M. M. Styrov analyze the adaptation of the forest complex of the Komi Republic to unfavorable foreign economic conditions in 2022–2023. The researchers emphasize the primarily negative consequences of sanctions, including the loss of foreign markets, rising costs of financial resources, and difficulties in obtaining imported components [8].

I. V. Kharionovskaya examines the state of forest resources in the Komi Republic. The author identified areas of the forest fund where reforestation is economically feasible and assessed their potential economic impact. Forests were grouped, and the condition and development prospects of each group were described [9].

S. Senko and J. Pykäläinen analyze the opinions of experts from Russian logging companies regarding forestry development, using the Republic of Karelia as a case study. The results indicate that technological, political, and economic factors had the greatest impact on companies, while social and environmental considerations were secondary [10].

The Russian forestry industry is actively adopting new technologies, such as remote sensing, geographic information systems (GIS), automated forest resource accounting systems, and robotic solutions.

V. Shapkin et al. note that a key milestone will be the launch in 2025 of the Federal State Information System of the Forestry Complex, which will integrate advanced technologies such as remote sensing, artificial intelligence, and blockchain. The use of satellite and drone data, combined with management automation and big data analytics, will enhance the efficiency and sustainability of forestry, which is vital for both environmental protection and national economic interests [11].

E. Skvorcova et al. discuss the use of IoT technologies in Russian forestry, highlighting applications for fire detection, illegal logging prevention, and optimization of logging operations [12].

A. Boitsov et al. emphasize the importance of automated robotic systems specifically designed for forest management in Russia, detailing technological aspects of their implementation in the sector. Applications include forest planting and firefighting [13].

S. N. Bareiko and S. K. Kravchenko stress that the introduction and development of digital technologies in forestry remain urgent, as practical forestry depends on high-quality, accessible, and comprehensive information about forest resources. They argue that the widespread adoption of digital technologies will improve the reliability, completeness, and accessibility of forest information [14].

A. Ivanova investigates the availability and development of innovative infrastructure in scientific and educational organizations related to forestry. The author finds that leading institutions in developing and transferring innovative technologies and equipment within the timber industry are those with well-established innovation infrastructure [15].

Finally, business interest in investing in timber industry projects and sustainable resource management remains crucial.

S. Morkovina et al. presented the results of a survey of entrepreneurs evaluating the effectiveness of forest management in Russia. The authors found that more than half of the respondents consider their forestry businesses unprofitable. The researchers argue that regional-level incentive mechanisms can support tenants of forest plots who engage in high-quality forestry activities [16].

L. Pronyaeva et al. examine organizational and economic processes in the Russian forest sector and timber industry, including regional variations. The researchers suggest that creating interregional clusters in the forest sector, aligned with a "smart specialization" model for spatial development, can enhance efficiency. Establishing interregional cooperation among forestry enterprises increases operational efficiency, facilitates large-scale innovative projects, promotes rational forest resource use, and stimulates economic activity [17].

A. V. Kolesnikova evaluates the potential of Russia's forest resources and identifies key directions for their use. The scientist argues that implementing the ecosystem functions of forests should be a central focus in developing a modern forest management strategy. Conditions should be created that encourage businesses to participate in forest-climatic projects [18].

O. Netrebskaya studies investment projects in Russia's forest complex. The researcher highlights the significant untapped development potential and low investment attractiveness for businesses. Netrebskaya identifies public-private partnerships as the most effective mechanism for attracting investment in forest-climatic projects [19].

N. Gorshenina examines the impact of investment risks on the economic performance of forestry enterprises in Russia. The author concludes that prioritizing strategic and tactical development should involve creating a circular economy based on renewable forest resources [20].

Overall, the analysis of sources underscores the importance of attracting investment through public-private partnerships and developing a circular economy grounded in renewable forest resources. The authors note prospects for digitalization and innovative development in Russian forestry. Implementing digital technologies is essential for improving the reliability of forest resource information; well-developed innovative infrastructure in scientific and educational institutions is crucial for creating and transferring new technologies in the forestry industry.

RESULTS

In April-May 2020, a period marked by stringent measures, numerous Russian timber industry enterprises were forced to halt operations for 1.5-2 months. Recovery in the second half of 2020 offset the decline experienced in the first half, enabling the domestic timber industry to achieve positive revenue growth (+10% YoY).

Figure 1 Imports and exports of wood, pulp, and paper products in Russia, 2015-2022. Compiled by the authors according to sources: [21, p. 765-766 and other collections of articles]

After the 2020 “bottom” in production and consumption of forest products, 2021 showed robust recovery, with demand reaching peak levels and growth in the housing sector supporting higher prices. The Russian timber industry achieved record results in 2021:

- Enterprise revenue grew 32% year-on-year;
- Net profit tripled to 460 billion RUB, and the timber industry's contribution to GDP rose to 2%.

However, sanctions and the resulting drop in exports to 11,990.2 million USD by the end of 2022, compared with 16,994.4 million USD in 2021, set the timber industry back five years, returning it to the 2017 level (see Chart 1). This shift highlights the interconnectedness of the global economy and the supply chains it forms.

The redistribution of sales markets in 2021 occurred amid a sharp decline in prices in both global and domestic markets, alongside a slowing global economy as part of the wider recession. Consequently, as shown in Table 1, Russian timber industry revenue in 2022 fell 10.3% year-on-year, with particularly sharp declines in certain segments, for example, plywood production dropped by 28.7%.

Table 1

Russian timber industry development trends, 2010-2022

Name	2010	2015	2016	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2022-2010,%	Rel. rev. in 2021-2022, %
Timber, sawn or split longitudinally, either layered or peeled, over 6 mm thick; wooden railway or tram sleepers, untreated, thousand m ³	21890	22030	23791	29713	29967	29299	32333	29000	132.48	-10.31
Plywood, thousand m ³	2697	3657	3837	4121	4146	4198	4550	3241	120.17	-28.77
Wood pulp and pulp from other fibrous materials, thousand tons	7510	7875	8208	8585	8245	8761	8877	8767	116.74	-1.24
Paper and cardboard, thousand tons	7659	3121	8467	9148	9159	9718	10404	10109	131.99	-2.83

Compiled by the authors according to sources: [21, p. 765-766, etc.]

Adjusting supply terms for foreign markets required the implementation of support measures, primarily compensating for export transportation costs. In February 2023, the maximum subsidy for exporting pulp and paper products was raised from 300 million RUB to 500 million RUB, with 100% compensation for shipments through Russia's northwestern ports.

In 2021, Russia reduced the volume of wood and wood product exports by 24.3% to 8,974.9 million USD. Imports of wood and related products decreased slightly (by 2.7%) to 784.9 million USD. Within highly redistributed product categories, exports of paper, cardboard, and related products fell 4.6% YoY to 3,015.4 million USD, and by the end of 2022 decreased by 3.2% YoY to 2,617 million USD [22].

Export shipments grew in the category of wood pulp (+15.2%), reaching \$1,611.4 million, while imports contracted by 22.1% to 191.4 million USD.

The reduction of paper and cardboard exports from Russia to the EU in 2022 by 41.1% YoY was accompanied by increased shipments to China, particularly from the Ilim Group. The share of the enterprise's exports to southwestern China is projected to rise from 5% to 16% by 2025, and overall shipments to China may grow by more than half [23].

Notably, the "new" geography of Russian exports in 2022 was shaped by the unprecedented growth of the timber export sector in 2021 (see Fig. 1), partly due to extended lockdowns in Western countries and disruptions to established supply

chains, which sharply increased demand for pulp and paper products. As shown in Table 1, peak production levels across all product categories in Russia occurred in 2021, when government support measures stimulated demand for furniture and related products in the second half of 2020. Exports declined in 2019 due to a contraction in domestic consumption of Russian products in China, driven by the trade war with the United States and the devaluation of the yuan, which reduced the price competitiveness of imports. The subsequent pandemic further exacerbated this downward trend.

Sanctions, the restructuring of export-oriented supply chains, and the challenges of replacing Western markets with Asian buyers demonstrate how tightly integrated modern economies are into global production and sales networks [24].

As R.V. Gordeev and A.I. Pyzhev note, “The damage to countries imposing restrictions on Russia is also significant. Russia’s largest trading partners in Europe – Finland, Germany, and the Baltic states – will suffer the most. At the same time, a sharp rise in logging in the EU amid the energy crisis creates a medium-term opportunity for the Russian forestry sector” [25, pp. 45-46].

Exports create additional market opportunities, prompting capacity expansion and increased business funding. Promotion of products and consolidation of supplier brands in global regional markets forms the basis for competitive positioning and scaling of sales. Such market maneuvers are more complex in high-value-added sectors, such as the pulp and paper industry, which generates over 40% of the gross value added of Russian timber products.

In 2021, the development of domestic timber product exports secured Russia a position among the world’s top 20 exporters of paper and cardboard and placed it among the top three suppliers of newsprint, which in Russia are concentrated in the North-West and Volga federal districts.

The growth of the catering sector, the shift of food sales online, and the expansion of food production are gradually increasing the capacity of the domestic packaging market, which reached 1.3 trillion RUR in 2022 (compared to 1.2 trillion RUR in 2021). By 2025, the market could potentially grow by up to 30%, reaching 1.7 trillion RUR, which is expected to stimulate import substitution for both raw materials and packaging products. In the long term, this will reduce the ratio of exports to imports (in terms of raw materials), which currently stands at roughly two to one.

The suspension of foreign companies’ operations in Russia created “vacant” market capacity, giving Russian manufacturers an opportunity to expand

production and improve efficiency. In particular, LPK Ilim increased its capacity in 2021, producing 3.64 million tons of finished products, strengthening its share of the domestic packaging materials market. Segezha Pulp and Paper Mill JSC is actively investing 55 billion RUR in the construction of the world's largest softwood debarking and felling line [26].

Thus, the scale and intensity of sanctions necessitate structural restructuring across the entire production and commercial cycle of the domestic timber industry, affecting both manufacturing and trade.

This restructuring carries risks for domestic production of paper and cardboard containers, which in recent years has contributed to growth in Russian pulp and paper exports. Potential losses from sanctions can be broken down into several components:

1. Lost export revenues;
2. Disrupted domestic price stability. Since the end of February 2022, Russian manufacturers reduced production by 25% to avoid “forced” dumping, which occurs when additional production is sold at lower prices to attract orders, leading to profit loss.
3. Underutilization of capacities and reduced employment, as the decline in exports cannot be fully offset by redirecting products to the domestic market or to new international buyers [27].

The first component is especially significant due to the overall shift in the structure of Russian pulp and paper exports, where the share of minimally processed lumber increased from 2007 to 2009, complementing the strategy to reduce roundwood exports.

As N. E. Antonova notes, “The most significant growth in lumber over the past decade has resulted from incentives for higher-value-added production through federal priority investment projects. This increased output, but mostly in products with low processing levels” [28, p. 17].

The growth in exports of fiberboard, chipboard, plywood, and paper/cardboard containers boosted the overall added value. This trend persisted even during the acute phase of the 2020-2021 coronavirus crisis, when “exports of medium- and high-value-added products moderately declined or even increased, compared with a sharper reduction in low-value products” [25, p. 48].

Such structural shifts in industry supply occurred alongside anticipated departmental initiatives to ban exports of roundwood and certain lumber types [29, pp. 8-10].

To stimulate investment in the timber industry, at the end of 2019 the Ministry of Industry proposed reducing rates for enterprises with processing capacities and/or exporting timber products from 13% to 6.5% in 2020, which led to a reduction in roundwood export rates to 2.5% per year [Ibid., p. 8].

As a result, exports of unprocessed timber to China reached multi-year lows, while exports to Finland remained at long-term average levels.

The geography of processed timber exports is diversified:

- Export volumes are increasing to countries including Uzbekistan, Japan, Germany, and Azerbaijan.
- Tajikistan and Vietnam are emerging as new external markets.
- Exports to China are declining [Ibid., p. 9].

DISCUSSION

Overall, the analysis showed that sanctions and the forced shift away from the free-market model for forest and pulp and paper products create a challenging evolutionary loop in global market dynamics and institutionalization. At this stage of development, there are no beneficiaries able to pass through this cycle without losses or to quickly diversify their supply channels.

From the European Union's perspective, the Russian market was not the primary one. About one-third of the value of goods covered by the fifth sanctions package was exported to Russia from Finland, and roughly one-quarter from Germany [25, p. 58]. Considering the alignment of product types with the Russian sales market, the Baltic countries were particularly vulnerable, as their export flows were heavily concentrated on Russia.

For EU countries, sanctions impose a stronger macroeconomic constraint, producing several related adverse effects:

- a decline in domestic production competitiveness due to multiple increases in energy costs, which could lead to the bankruptcy of many European enterprises;
- Slower imports and rising prices for wheat and corn starch in the European

market, with almost one-third of domestic consumption tied to the EU pulp and paper industry. Globally, Russia and Ukraine account for 30% of wheat and 20% of corn supplies [30].

Even more significant for the EU timber industry is the blocking of imports from Russia, 38% of which previously came from Finland and Germany. In terms of importing raw materials for the Russian market, Finland and the Baltic countries were effectively closed.

Thus, globalization and the tight interconnection of sectoral markets across countries underscore the large-scale losses caused by the 2020 lockdowns and subsequent sanctions, which will exacerbate global commodity shortages.

For the Russian timber industry, the most pressing issue is the redistribution of export flows toward the southeast, particularly to Asian and Chinese markets.

The eastern shift in export geography faces several significant constraints:

- Higher logistics costs. According to Segezha Group calculations, restructuring new supply chains amid rising Russian Railways freight tariffs could increase costs by 2.5-4.7 times [25, p. 62];
- Increased risk of secondary sanctions from the EU and USA, slowing the trade activity of potential Asian partners;
- Limited capacity of ground transport infrastructure in eastern regions, making trade with China contingent on the availability of railway cars.

The conceptual conclusions of this study can be summarized in two critical points:

- despite opportunities to expand capacity in the Russian timber industry through exports, the sector's higher sensitivity to external shocks underscores the unreliability of the export-oriented model, especially amid heightened geopolitical tensions between Russia and the West, where the economy becomes a political bargaining tool;
- The primary "reserve" for timber industry growth lies in the expansion of the domestic market, in which China's internal production complex is currently developing [31].

In general, the stability of the Russian timber market can rely on several key drivers, including:

- Weak ruble, which slows imports;
- Higher global prices for forest products;
- Lower transport tariffs and optimized logistics for product delivery.

In the current phase of restructuring trade relations and supply chains, the main growth lever for the domestic timber industry lies in transport and logistics solutions that reduce large-scale commodity supply costs.

S. Yu. Ivshin explores this issue in depth, noting that “changes in the geography and export routes of industrial paper products are accompanied by significant supra-industry transformations within the country – relocated logistics capacities distribution, a shift from in-house leases to 3PL services, and so on” [32, p. 39-41].

CONCLUSION

All this allows us to conclude that the market must find a new balance in both the channels and volumes of supply, given the restructuring of pulp and paper mill supply chains. The expected outcome should be increased operational efficiency of transport and warehouse logistics in the wholesale channel, distribution of products through retail chains, and supply chains integrated into the distribution networks of food production and FMCG goods

From a broader perspective, sustained and substantial demand for pulp and paper products in the global market, including the EU, which is developing new import schemes via third countries and intermediary hubs, necessitates the development of a new growth model for domestic timber products. This model will allow for a more effective balance in the reliable distribution of goods between the domestic market and export shipments.

A global indicator of the importance of these changes is the radical restructuring of international logistics and the diversification of supply strategies, driven by the localization of supplies and the reduction of one-sided dependence on China. The level of industrialization and urbanization in China no longer reproduces the macroeconomic effects of reducing commodity purchase prices seen in the early 2000s and especially the 1990s, when the spontaneous development of shuttle trade in Russia effectively financed industrialization in Northern China.

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The authors have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Arif G. Ibragimov. Russian State Agrarian University – Moscow Timiryazev Agricultural Academy (Russia)